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Abstract

This research paper is the outcome of a qualitative research method of reviewing relevant literature pertaining to a project namely the “SAFA Quetta project that aims to introduce a well managed mechanism of solid waste collection, cleaning to roads and streets to improve environment degradation for inhabitants of Quetta city. The project

was launched in 2024 by a model of Public-Private-Partnership PPP under the supervision of Quetta Metropolitan Corporation QMC. This study strived to explore the perspectives and prospects of the project with regard to its efficiency, effectiveness and sustainability while suggesting pragmatic actions to be taken by its executor and stakeholder both at policy and implementation level. A large number of relevant literatures were reviewed, analyzed and compared with the existing mechanism of services delivery. For sustenance of project aspects such as community participation level, transparency and accountability mechanism were explored and analyzed with regard to project implementation. Opinions of relevant stakeholders were also incorporated through focus group discussions sessions. At the end a critical report is prepared for general public and in particular for project executors to be incorporated into project activities.

Keywords: Urban sanitation, community engagement, public-private partnership, qualitative evaluation, Quetta, Pakistan

Introduction

Solid Waste Management had always been a major issue in many major cities of the country including the provincial capital of Balochistan, Quetta. Apart from outdated routine cleaning services being provided by Municipal Corporation, various small scale initiatives have since long been initiated

by various NGOs in different localities of the city, but with limited scope and area of operation ([Wasi-ud-Din, 2018](#)). Almost all of these waste management initiative were by and large limited to only primary collection of household waste management, not its sorting and final disposal. The final disposal of the collected waste was to be performed by the municipal corporation. Indeed urban sanitation and rapid population, air and noise pollution and similar associated issues are now considered one of the major characteristics of rapidly growing major cities of developing countries. Quetta, the capital of Balochistan province, exemplifies this challenge. As the largest city in Pakistan's most underdeveloped province, which has long grappled with inadequate waste management systems, deteriorating drainage infrastructure, and the public health consequences of environmental degradation ([Government of Balochistan, 2024](#)) Safa Project was launched to address this major issues in August 2024 with the aim to over this issue through public- private partnership indeed with active community participation.

Prior to highlighting the modalities of Safa project, Quetta Kachi Abadi Environmental Management Program QKAEMP funded by Netherlands and executed by 6 implementing partners was successfully introduced a model of community based sanitation, waste management and hygiene improvement in 47 informal settlement in the city with the prime objective of sustainable partnership between communities and local government. This project successfully completed lying of more than 100000rft of low cost sanitation throughout the slum areas of Quetta city during 1997-2003. As an outcome and legacy of the project which was observed in surveys conducted as post project activity revealed that active community participation is a key to improving the poor living environment and addressing the infrastructure gaps in urban informal settlements ([QKAEMP Survey Report, 2005](#)). Late on activities designed to be executed pertaining to waste management and low cost sanitation got almost non functional as a result of non-functionality of lane organizations (A sort of Community Based Organization) initially formed by the implementing partner of the project for execution and smooth functioning of the QKAEMP project. In few areas such as Marriabad, Hazara Town, Cantonment Board Areas and some

part of downtown areas of city waste collection is still functional, however by private entities as reported during key informant interviews (Ali, 2025).

Safa project, no doubt is another major shift from conventional approaches to an effective urban sanitation effort in Pakistan. The project integrates solid waste management framework with infrastructural development—including the deployment of 217 vehicles and machinery, establishment of 128 temporary waste dumping points, and daily cleaning of 640 kilometers of streets—with community outreach programming that includes school-based awareness sessions and door-to-door collection services . The initiative has generated over 1,200 employment opportunities, positioning sanitation work within a formal employment framework (Associate Press of Pakistan, APP, 14th July, 2025) .Another aspect of Safa project seemingly vivid is that it has political support and will of ruling government. Mir Sarfraz Bugti has articulates in a press briefing that the project is a flagship initiative of transforming Quetta into a "model city" with modern urban facilities. This political commitment has translated into high-level oversight, with regular review meetings and directives to remove "longstanding garbage piles from every neighborhood" (APP, 15th October, 2025). However, expert opinions emphasize that engagement of private sector and community is not confine a procedural add-on, but a critical determinant of project sustainability (Khan, 2013). In Pakistan, institutionalized participatory mechanisms have historically faced challenges related to elite capture, lack of awareness, and weak accountability systems (Khan, 2013). The Safa Quetta Project's explicit emphasis on community outreach and civic pride therefore warrants careful examination of how engagement strategies are operationalized and experienced.

The public-private partnership model adopted by the Safa Quetta Project represents an effort to address these institutional weaknesses by combining government support with private sector expertise and efficiency. Proponents argue that such partnerships can bring greater accountability, resource mobilization, and technical capacity to municipal services (World Bank, 2020). However, critics caution that PPPs in developing country contexts may prioritize cost-recovery over equity, potentially marginalizing

poorer neighborhoods and informal settlements where service delivery is most challenging (Miraftab, 2004).

The Balochistan Context

Balochistan, geographically the biggest and smallest in term of populace is least developed and confront unique developmental challenges. The province has historically lagged behind others in human development indicators, with limited infrastructure, weak institutional capacity, and ongoing security concerns (Asian Development Bank, 2024). Quetta, as the provincial capital, concentrates many of these challenges while also serving as a site of political contestation and civic activism. Recent reports from local political parties have raised concerns about corruption and inadequate service delivery under the Safa Quetta Project, highlighting the contested nature of urban governance in the city.

Methodology

This research paper is a preliminary effort towards in-depth research studies in future. The present study is qualitative in its very nature as for the most part the already available literature pertaining to Safa project and solid waste management procedure were reviewed, analyzed and conclusion were drawn. Apart from secondary data analysis two consecutive sessions of focus group discussions were conducted whose participants were relevant stakeholders of the project both from policy makers, project workers and key informant community elders and target group of the project. Since exploring community perceptions and experiences is appropriate method therefore qualitative method best suits the research paper by quantifying the qualitative data and information (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). However, multiple efforts has been made to ensure diversity and heterogynous group (individual from different background) As experts suggest that in order to receive informed and well thought opinions while keeping in view the complexity and sensitivity of the stakeholders perceptive (Nicholas et al., 2024).

Findings / Results

Like many other program and project being initiated by Government, particularly local government i.e. Quetta Metropolitan Corporation QMC the project seems an ideal project to address the multifaceted issues of environmental degradation. However, on ground realities do not match with

what Safa project was initially conceived. There gaps in terms of resource allocation, trained human resources and final treatment of solid waste collection right from primary collection, to disposal points, from disposal points to sorting of waste collection and to its final disposal at dump side.

Ownership of the project by stakeholders including project staff, the general public and media support is a major challenge which is evident. Ownership ensures active participation of all stakeholders, which is the utmost and significant need of the project for its successful implementation, effectiveness and beyond all its sustainability.

Monitoring mechanism though encompasses as an integral part of the project, absence of local body representative as Nazim and Councilors are the missing aspect of the project. An elected body representative can better monitoring and identify the missing aspects and gaps in the operational aspect for its better execution and sustainability of the imitative

There is also a wide gap between informal leadership such as key well informed citizens, media persons, civil society organization, course contents of educational institutions vis-à-vis Safa project

The soft package of project pertaining to creation and sensitization of masses is another major missing aspect. Majority of the masses in almost all part of city do contribute in generating solid wastes, but there is a dearth of taking responsibility to manage their conventional though of producing least waste and opt for three (R) of recycle, reuse and refuse.

Discussion

The findings of this research project concludes a wide gap between target groups of the project as for the time being it covers for the most part the elite segment of population, peripheral neighborhoods and informal human settlements are least approached where waste generation is comparatively large in quantity, environmental degradation is more severe and social awareness regarding healthy and hygienically life style is almost absent. Whereas, the existing model of public- private partnership must adhere to a holistic approach to be adopted. This pattern aligns with concerns raised in the literature about PPPs potentially prioritizing cost-effective, high-return areas over more challenging, lower-density contexts (MirafTAB, 2004).

From the complex theoretical perspective any gap in implementation strategy such as focus one part and ignoring the others might not work as

its create hindrance towards ownership. Flexibility in implementation strategy among communities must be considered on priority basis as one strategy might be success story somewhere, but might not work elsewhere due to diversity on various basis including economic status, ethnic background and level of education (Patton, 2011).

A previous study undertaken by a private firm has beautifully articulated the following pragmatic tasks to be incorporated into the existing project design and practices

- Safa projects must develop systematic mechanisms for monitoring for equity in service delivery, tracking performance across different types of neighborhoods and adjusting resource allocation to address gaps. This might include regular community surveys stratified by neighborhood type, with results publicly reported.
- Second, special efforts need to be made to develop model of ensuring active community participation while considering the diversity of formal and informal human settlements. And this engagement must be a two way process to add on inputs from local body representatives and general masses in operational phases of the project.
- Third, complaint and feedback mechanisms should be simplified, with clear pathways for residents to raise concerns and receive responses. Transparency about institutional responsibilities—who does what—could help residents navigate the system.
- Fourth, communication strategies should balance celebration of achievements with acknowledgment of ongoing challenges, building trust through honesty and responsiveness.
- Finally, attention to sanitation workers' conditions—including timely payment, safety equipment, and recognition—is essential for service quality and worker dignity (Qureshi, 2023).

Conclusion

While concluding, the result and discussion points of this research express a wide gulf between perception and actual project implementation of Safa Quetta project. Despite the fact that the project proved to be an effort of paradigm shift from conventional waste management to a well thought urban environmental management program both at policy and implementation level regarding proper solid waste management, sweeping

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of roads, disposing of collected waste into final disposal point. The project has achieved significant infrastructural milestones and generated visible improvements in formal neighborhoods, contributing to civic pride and engagement. Nevertheless, a large scale project like “Safa Quetta” to be executed in a major metropolitan city, which is characterized by prevailing fragile institutional capacity, political instability, poor socioeconomic condition and security concern is not complex, but difficult too. Recent scholarship on complex public health and urban development interventions emphasizes that such initiatives require evaluation approaches sensitive to context, adaptation, and community perspectives (Nicholas et al., 2024). As Nicholas and colleagues (2024) argue, "complex interventions are intentionally flexible, making them challenging to evaluate with predetermined measures" and necessitate qualitative methods that can capture unanticipated outcomes and indirect ripple effects

However, uneven implementation between formal and informal settlements is inconsistent, which might hinder project’s prospects. Community engagement efforts show promise, particularly school-based awareness sessions, but creating awareness among schooled audiences though easy, the majority unschooled audiences have not been yet targeted. This shows a major drawback, special communication materials, to reach unschooled audience must be developed both in print and electronic media. Apart from mainstream media, social media outlets must be engaged to sensitize masses for active participation, project’s effectiveness and sustainability of the program (The Express Tribune, Nov. 6th 2024).

It is also imperative to develop a well functioning monitoring mechanism ideally by holding elections of local bodies and by delegating the task and authority to elected representative for effectiveness and success of the project. Transparency and accountability mechanism must also be revisited to make a successful model to be replicated in other districts of the province and cities of the entire country. As the project continues to expand and evolve, ongoing community engagement and complexity-sensitive evaluation can help ensure that the vision of a "cleaner, greener, and more livable city” becomes a reality for all residents of Quetta. Future research should be conducted from time to time as an integral part of “Research and Development RD” model to examine long-term project

outcomes, explore the perspectives of project managers and government officials, and investigate the sustainability of behavioral changes. Comparative studies across other Pakistani cities implementing similar reforms could illuminate contextual factors that shape success (World Bank, 2020).

Finally, the Safa Quetta project should not be confined to waste collection and cleaning/ sweeping of roads, streets and lane. The project must further explore methods pertaining to sorting of collected and adding values to valuable items for its reuse, recycle and even producing new household items and manmade materials for daily use. At the final disposal point there are possibilities of converting the collected into useful organic fertilizer.

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